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**THE SITUATION OF THE LIGHT INDUSTRY IN THE OVER DNIPRO UKRAINE
IN THE SECOND HALF OF XIX-th – EARLY XX-th CENTURY**

The article highlights the question of the formation and the development of the light industry in the Over Dnipro Ukraine in the second half of XIX-th – early XX-th century and their impact on the socio-economic development of the region. The issue of the unresolved crisis phenomena in the light industry is a special interest in the society and among scientifics to the economic problems in the national economy. The processes that were in Ukraine in the past require profound analytical and synthesized assessments by historians today. The article carries materials about the industrial development of the factories and plants, it was shown the supply of raw materials for the enterprises. It was specified the industrial directions of the factories because of scientific achievements and the sales on export and domestic markets. It is presented the general situation of some branches of the light industry. Studying this subject it was found that the network of the plants and

factories was formed both by the efforts of the government schemes and local businessmen. It is realized the reasons of the decline of the industry due to increased demand for tilled soil, decrease of the raw materials and the production transfer from Ukraine. The history of the light industry was one of the actual topics not only from the scientific and cognitive point of view, but also in the context of identifying the historical roots of modern problems and ways of their solution. It was emphasized that the processes of the formation and development of the light industry in the Ukrainian provinces had their own specificity in comparison with the general-imperial tendencies.

Key words: *light industry, market, raw materials, plant, technical progress, commodity-money relations, reforms, factory-plant industry.*

The issue of unresolved crisis phenomena in the light industry is a special interest in society and scientific circles to economic problems. The processes that took place in Ukraine in the past require profound analytical and synthesized assessments by historians today. Modern Ukrainian economy requires the study of specific experience in the management and development of the light industry in the second half of the XIX-th and early XX-th centuries. Therefore, at this stage of the historical science, a comprehensive understanding of the peculiarities of the development of the light industry in Ukraine involves studying the problems of economic history and its separate regions. The formation and development of the light industry in the Ukrainian provinces had their own specificity in comparison with the general imperial tendencies. The experience of the economy has shown that it is the light industry that can quickly adapt to activities in the market conditions. The situation of the light industry can not be imagined in isolation from such elements of the economy as trade, co-operation, private capital, taxes, customs policy, pricing, markets. The maturity of these elements, the level of their introduction into economic relations directly depended from the degree of practical implementation of the reforms of the 1860's in all spheres of vital activity of the state.

The works of historians who studied some branches of the light industry have made their contribution into the studies of the Ukrainian light industry. The works about light industry appeared relatively long ago and in their nature have only a general outline of the main processes of the light industry development in Ukraine. The need for a deeper and more comprehensive study of the structure, organization, level of industrial production requires the expansion of the source base. Historiographic works of this issue consider light industry in the context of the policy of the tsarist government, its role in the economic development of Russia and Ukraine is significant in the study of the topic. The work of T. Derevyankin [7] is devoted to the study of a separate form of industry (manufactory) on the example of its most characteristic branch (textile). The monograph has become a study of the Ukrainian textile manufactory, it solves a complex set of questions about the patterns of formation and development of the textile industry in Ukraine in the general aspect of the genesis of capitalism. Much attention was paid to the situation of Russian and Ukrainian light industry by K. Pajitnov [13; 14]. The author connects the formation of the wool, silk and flax hemp industry with the economic and customs policies of the autocracy regarding to the establishment of the enterprises and the provision them by raw materials. I. Gurzhia's monograph [5] covers a complex of issues about the expansion and strengthening of the industrial and commercial development of Ukraine in the 60–90's of the XIX-th century. In particular, the author highlights the development of the light industry in Ukraine in the system of formation of market relations. O. Nesterenko showed the industry of Ukraine on the all main stages of its development: the period of the development of industry from craft to the factory and the development of factory production in pre-revolutionary Ukraine [10]. The problems of the formation of Ukrainian light industry and the marketing of its products was researched by M. Moskaluk [8]. The author analyzed the economic policy of tsarism with regard to the light industry, its material and technical base and production volumes. A monograph of Kharkiv researchers dedicated to the Kharkiv rope plant [2] became

a great work in the study of regional history. It traces the development of the plant since its foundation up to 70-ies of the XX-th century by the merchant Novikov. However, the analysis of available literature indicates that the problems of the situation of the light industry of the investigated period have not been fully studied.

The purpose of the study is to reveal the situation of the light industry of the Over Dnipro Ukraine in the second half of the XIX-th and early XX-th centuries through analysis of the development of its industries, the productivity and machining of factories and plants.

The research tasks are to determine the state of scientific development of the problem and directions of its elucidation, to clarify the peculiarities of the light industry development; the disclosure of its dynamics, the impact of the reforms on the economic climate and the industrial development of the Ukrainian provinces of the Russian Empire.

As a result of the reform of 1861 new market relations changed the old feudal ones. Under these conditions, the merchants and nobles of the Over Dnipro Ukraine were actively involved into the development of commodity production. The light industry which was most represented by wool cloth, wool stockings and wool washing branches was no exception in the studied region.

The light industry of the Ukrainian provinces of the Russian Empire had its own peculiarities. The development of the most important branches of production largely depended from the imported equipment, raw materials and materials. Many sectors of the light industry did not exist at all [6, p. 9]. Some branches of the light industry, which in the pre-reform period came to the external market with their products began to decline during the period of industrial capitalism, they developed very slowly, working on a narrow domestic market. They were cloth and rope industries [5, p. 42].

The industry of the processing of fibrous matter was the most developed. This industry includes a set of industries involved in the processing of plant and animal fibers. In the study period, the wool industry fell into three large and completely separate branches of wool production: coarse cloth, thin cloth and wool worsted fabrics. The main group of the wool industry were factories for making cloth. The enterprises engaged in the production of wollen fabrics can be divided into two groups. The first group included institutions that fabricated rude army cloths at a price of about 1 rub. for the arshin. These enterprises were located in the Katerynoslav, Poltava, Kharkiv and Kherson provinces. The concentration of cloth production in the Ukrainian provinces was caused by a large raw material base in the south of Ukraine and it was easy to deliver it by navigable rivers [13, p. 81].

The second group consisted of worsted enterprises, including stockings. The first manufactory, producing worsted fabrics, arose in Russia in 1826 in Ryga, later the production of fabrics was developed in Moscow. The manufactory of General Popkov operated in Katerynoslav, but it was closed. The spread of the production of worsted fabrics was greatly hampered by the lack of long-fiber wool, the high complexity of preparatory operations and the high cost of spinning devices. The second group included institutions located in Volyn, Kyiv, Podillya, Tavriya and Chernihiv provinces. By their size they gave way to the enterprises of the first group, but the cost of production per worker was almost 4 times higher. The cost per leg of wool was 2 rubles 26 kopecks, which is more than 2 times higher. The manufactories of these provinces provided local middle class by the products and exported it [13, p. 73–84].

The third group of companies included wool washing and sorting facilities of the wool industry. The primary processing of wool was carried out in the Kharkiv and Kherson provinces. At the beginning of the XX-th century, there were 2 wool washing machines in the Kharkiv province that were founded in 1850 and in 1875, and the sinks, which were mentioned in the lists in 1894 and 1898, were established in 1824 and 1844. In 1878 they were closed. Thus, the closing of old and the lack of new enterprises were observed in wollen production. The productivity of each closed wollen washing factory was about 25–30 thousand pounds of wool a year [11, p. 5].

The production of wollen industry in the pre-reform period was spread not only in Ukraine, but also in Central Russia, the Baltic provinces, the Kingdom of Poland, in the Caucasus, gradually reduced its production. By the 70's of the XIX-th century more than half of wollen products were manufactured in the Moscow province. Six provinces followed it, each of which produced industrial products for 2,5–8 million rubles. Their number included the Chernihiv province. The Kyyiv province belonged to eight provinces of Russia with the cost of production from 500 to 1800 thousand rubles. In the Podilsk and Volyn provinces, the manufacture of wool products was from 100 to 300 thousand rubles. In 1895 in the Ukrainian provinces there were 194 cloth enterprises, the cost of their production was 3280 thousand rubles, or 313 thousand rubles less than in 1865. This was the consequence of those shifts that took place in the economic specialization of the areas [5, p. 42–43].

The textile industry in the Ukrainian provinces was not developed enough before the First World War. For its successful development it was necessary to fulfill three main requirements: the opportunity to receive cheap raw materials, sufficient fuel reserves and cheap labour. According to the first point, Ukraine did not differ much from Central Russia, but to deliver cotton from America or Egypt was very unnecessary. The utilization of the development of peat deposits in Ukraine and the development of deposits of coal in Russia, placed the Ukrainian industry in a disadvantage too. And if you consider that Ukraine had always been an agricultural land, then, of course, there were not enough free hands. By these reasons, the textile industry, historically, was not in the southern state, but in the north, in the so-called Central region of Russia. It is no coincidence that in 1912 the textile industry of Ukraine occupied the whole industry: by the number of enterprises 1,8%, by the number of workers – 0,9%, by the output of production – 0,6% [14, p. 232].

In Ukraine the textile industry was less developed compared to other industrial productions, and it remained the same until the beginning of the First World War. As in the first half of the XIX-th century, Ukraine was the market for the sale of textiles from the central and northern regions of Russia and Poland. Ukraine was also a rich source of raw materials for the textile industry of Russia. Comparing the industrial development of Russia and Ukraine, it can be affirmed that the manufacturing and textile industries occupied the leading place in Russia, while in the Over Dnipro Ukraine the textile industry was at eleventh place. By 1914 there were only 6 large textile enterprises in Ukraine: 3 in Kharkiv, 2 in Odesa and 1 in Lugansk. In Kharkiv two wool washing machines used Ukrainian and imported raw materials from the Caucasus and one sink-rope factory. The Black Sea roped plant and the jute factory worked in Odesa. In Lugansk there was a factory for the production of camel belts, transmission belts for mills, pressed cloth for olyans. During the First World War a part of textile enterprises were transported to Ukraine from Russia for the needs of the Army. The census of 1920 registered 126 enterprises (Kharkiv region 37, Odesa and Kyyiv regions 17). Only 68 enterprises could produce products because of the lack of necessary equipment [3, p. 13–14].

Wool washing factories appeared in Ukraine in connection with the development of the cloth industry and the growth of sheep breeding where wool was sorted steamed, washed in cold water, dried and packed in bales. The owners of the wool washing factories bought wool for the initial processing, resold it or washed for a payment from the landowners [4, p. 30].

Most of the wool which was delivered to the cloth factories was washed and cleaned. The main raw material for the production of high-quality cloth was thin-wool. Kharkiv became the center of the wollen industry for merino wool from the second half of the XIX-th century. In 1860 there were 7 wool washing factories operating there. They were the best in the Russian Empire with their equipments and quantity of washed wool. Almost 700 workers worked at the best merchants of Kuvshinnikov's and Ryzhov's enterprises. The cash turnover of each of the entrepreneurs was in the amount of 300–400 thousand rubles only for one summer. Total working capital of all enterprises amounted to 600 thousand rubles; the annual output in cash

equivalent reached 1 million rubles, or 26% of the same indicator throughout the Russian Empire (3 million 856 thousand rubles). Except Ukraine washed wool was sold to wollen factories in Moscow and abroad (Austria, Prussia). In the early 60's of the XIX-th century the wool washing industry played an important role in Kharkiv industry, over 2 thousand workers worked at all wool washing factories [16, p. 73].

During the investigated period, the number of wollen enterprises and workers on them decreased, and the volume of production decreased too. At the same time an intensive process of concentration, mechanization of production and the growth of the labour productivity took place on this basis. If in 1865 one enterprise produced the output amounted to 232 897 rubles, then in 1895 – 648 100 rubles. In that case, the volume of production of one company was almost threefold. So, the wool washing production in the Kherson province was constantly decreasing, and it was growing in the Kharkiv province. By 1900, there were only 4 operating wool washing enterprises in Ukraine, 3 –in the Kharkiv province (686 workers), and 1 – in Kherson province (148 workers) [9, p. 54].

The rope-jute industry was developed thanks to the cheap raw materials and simple technical production. The Russian government developed it in Odesa for two reasons. In this largest Ukrainian port city there was a great demand for the sack-rope products which were necessary for technical equipment for the export of corn and other products. The second reason was the convenience of delivering imported jute to Odesa, which greatly reduced the price of the product itself. The advantageous location of Kharkiv on the border between areas rich in hemp and areas of high demand for sacks and other knitting had a positive influence on the distribution of the cable-jute industry in that centre. In comparison with the production of the Russian Empire, the share of the Ukrainian cable-and-jute industry in the total volume of production of yarn and other fibrous substances of vegetable origin approached to 20% [3, p. 14].

The cost of annual production of the rope industry was no more than 500 thousand rubles in the pre-reform period. Thus, in 1871, there were 9 rope enterprises working in the Poltava, Kharkiv, Katerynoslav and Kherson provinces, which employed 230 workers, who made ropes for 431 thousand rubles. Among rope companies, there were large plants with dozens and hundreds of workers. For example, Novikov's factory in Odesa produced 32 thousand pounds of ropes and strings in 1885. The raw material was brought from the Orel, Kursk and Chernihiv provinces, as well as from England (manila yarn). The ropes and strings made at the factory were sold to the Black Sea and Azov ports, and abroad to the ports of the Danube, the Aegean and the Mediterranean seas [5, p. 43]. The Ukrainian linen-cannabis-jute industry was 37,1% or 6% relatively to the same Russian Empire industry [1, p. 31].

Two largest centres of the Ukrainian leather industry were formed in Odesa and Berdychiv, they produced 9/10 of all products. It should be noted that full production could not develop in Ukraine as a result of the colonial situation of the economy. In that case, it is necessary to point out the sharp disproportion between leather raw materials and the production of semi-finished products. Analyzing the share of exports of leather raw materials beyond the boundaries of the ethnographic territory of Ukraine, we also observe that such soft leather goods as chrome, chevrolet, and others occupied a large proportion in the import balance. According to estimates, 1/3 of the consumed semi-finished products of the Ukrainian light industry were imported. The share of imported semi-finished and tannery materials was about 75% in the balance of the raw materials at the plants in Kyiv and Odesa. At the same time, Ukraine exported a significant amount of raw materials from the same regions. In despite of the shortage of the imported soft leather goods the production of solid (soled) semi-finished products amounted to 80% of the total production of semi-finished products. Such an irrational structure of the leather industry of the Over Dnipro Ukraine could not bring high profits [3, p. 13].

The largest enterprises of the leather production were in the Kyiv, Chernihiv and Kherson provinces. The number of factories and their annual production was almost the same in the Kyiv and Chernihiv provinces: 62 plants in the Chernihiv province made products for 1 386 000 rubles, 58 plants in the Kyiv province – for 1229 thousand rubles. The centres of the leather industry of the Kyiv province were Kyiv, Berdychiv and Smila. In the Berdychiv district there was the Schlenker's plant, which was founded in 1875, there were two steam engines (75 horsepower). Annual turnover reached 33 300 processed skin for the amount of 320 thousand rubles. There were 127 workers at the plant. The Kobets' plant in the suburbs of Kyiv was smaller with its production for 100 thousand rubles. It had a steam engine (20 horsepower) and 24 workers. The amount of processed leather was 16 500. The plants with small-scale production from 3 to 25 thousand rubles predominated in the Chernihiv province. The leather industry of the Kherson province had 16 factories with 475 workers, that produced the output for 1070 thousand rubles, it was mainly concentrated in Odesa. Paraskev and Koadazaki had the largest plants. The Paraskeva's plant had 2 steam engines for 30 horsepower, it produced 21 500 skins worth 400 thousand rubles, and it had 117 workers. The Koadazaki's plant operated two steam engines and 38 workers and it processed 36 200 skins a year, worth 362 thousand rubles. In the Yelysavetgrad county, the Olviopolskyi Leather Plant produced 12 thousand skins worth 180 thousand rubles; the plant operated one steam engine and 70 workers [15, p. 99].

It is difficult to statistically determine the volume of Ukrainian leather products on the eve of the First World War. Thus, according to the All-Russian Society of Garberneys, 16 million skins were produced (12,5 million large and 3,5 million small ones) in the Russian Empire in 1916. Ukraine accounted only 3 million, or 18,7% of this volume. In connection with the military actions some parts of the Russian leather plants were transferred to Ukraine. The demand for leather products was increasing. In this transition period, the share of Ukrainian products increased to 20–24% [3, p. 13].

Thus, on the eve of the First World War, the light industry of Ukrainian provinces declined, a group of fibrous processing plants didn't receive significant development in Ukraine. Ukraine provided for its demand for wool, cotton and other industrial goods by the products from the enterprises located in the other parts of the Russian Empire. Ukraine was also a rich source of raw materials for the textile and leather industry of Russia. The cotton industry wasn't developed in Ukraine, its small factories arised and disappeared in the different provinces. The fabric industry was represented by relatively large enterprises, it was located compactly, and mainly focused in the Poltava and Chernihiv provinces. Even technically-developed cloth factories didn't progress in the Chernihiv province and the quality of the products decreased in the second half of the XIX-th century. The wool washing industry that declined in the second half of the XIX-th century continued to play a significant role thanks to the development of this branch in the Kharkiv province. In the cable industry, only the Kharkiv rope factory and the Odesa jute factory were typical for developed capitalist enterprises. As an example the development of the leather industry shows the elements of the technical and economic falling of the Over Dnipro Ukraine.

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Левицький В. Становище легкої промисловості Наддніпрянської України в другій половині XIX – на початку XX ст.

У статті висвітлено питання формування та розвитку легкої промисловості у Наддніпрянській Україні в другій половині XIX – на початку XX ст. та її вплив на соціально-економічний розвиток регіону. Питання невирішеності кризових явищ у легкій промисловості викликає особливий інтерес у суспільстві та наукових колах для вирішення економічних проблем національної економіки. Процеси, що мали місце в Україні в минулому, вимагають сьогодні глибоких аналітичних та синтезованих оцінок істориків. У статті розкривається виробнича діяльність заводів і фабрик, показано постачання сировини для підприємств легкої промисловості. Вказані напрямки виробничої діяльності фабрик та заводів внаслідок наукових досягнень і продажів товарів на внутрішніх та зовнішніх ринках. У дослідженні представлено загальне становище деяких галузей легкої промисловості. Встановлено, що мережа заводів і фабрик формувалася як зусиллями державних структур, так і місцевими підприємцями. Виявлено причини зниження обсягів легкої промисловості через збільшення попиту на оброблювану землю, зменшення сировинних ресурсів та перенесення виробництва з України. Історія легкої промисловості була однією з актуальних тем не тільки з наукової та пізнавальної точок зору, але також у контексті виявлення історичних коренів сучасних проблем та шляхів їх вирішення. У статті підкреслено, що процеси формування та розвитку легкої промисловості в українських губерніях мали власну специфіку порівняно з загальноімперськими тенденціями.

Ключові слова: легка промисловість, ринок, сировина, завод, технічний прогрес, товарно-грошові відносини, реформи, фабрично-заводська промисловість.

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